

ANALYSIS OF FOLDS AND RECONNAISSANCE GEOLOGICAL MAPPING OF BUNDELKHAND MASSIFS AROUND MAHOBA DISTRICT (U.P)

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ABSTRACT: The Bundelkhand complex around Mahoba District is comprised of varied type of granites, gneisses, mafic dykes, metamorphites and volcanic sedimentary rocks of the middle Archean to Late Proterozoic. In the present research work geological study has been carried with special reference to analysis of folds in surroundings of Bijanagar Sagar, Paswara and Churbara areas situated in the eastern and southern part of Mahoba town. The rocks of the area have suffered folding, faulting and shearing. Grey granite, Pink granite, Porphyritic granite and Biotite granite form the dominant lithology of these areas. Gneisses are highly deformed and folded in nature. Gneissic enclaves are also found in pink granite at NW of Shahpahar. Amphibolite is observed in Paswara village within the gneisses. Dolerite is mainly oriented in NW-SE and forms prominent ridge surrounded by granite. The area is characterized by asymmetrical to symmetrical and isoclinal open folds. Quantitative analysis of hinge and limb thickness, and limb axial angle of naturally folded strata has been carried out and its implications for symmetrical fold genesis were used in elucidating the stages of folds. In this study 11 symmetrical folds were traced from various outcrops of Mahoba district.

KEYWORDS: Bundelkhand Massifs, Mahoba, Geological Mapping, Folds Analysis

1. INTRODUCTION: Central Indian shield is considered to be one of the regions on planet earth which preserved a record of the evolution and the history of the early crust having Archean-palaeoproterozoic rocks. There are four continental nuclei (Dharwar, Singhbhum, Aravalli and Bastar) with a protocontinental nucleus called the Bundelkhand craton in central India. The Bundelkhand Craton is bounded by Vindhyan Supergroup of rocks to the east, west and south. South-western fringe is marked by a relatively small outcrop of the Deccan trap basalt and the northern part is hidden under the Indo-Gangetic alluvium [1]. Geology of Bundelkhand complex has been described by number of workers [(2), (3), (4), (5), (6), (7)] who reported various rock types in the area. Meddicott (8) reported the occurrence of green stone dyke and quartz reef for the first time and suggested a prior origin for quartz reef. According to Pati et al. (1) more than 1500 mapable quartz veins/ reefs are presently exposed in the Bundelkhand Craton which is the most spectacular feature [9].

The field work have been carried out to record the geological attributes, structural data and rock sampling in the surrounding area of Bijanagar Sagar, Paswara and Churbara in Mahoba district (U.P.). For this purpose a number of traverses were taken along and across the exposures. The detailed geological and structural mapping was done on enlarged toposheet number 540/15 at 1:50,000 scale. Approximately 25 samples have been collected and various data pertaining to dip, strike, joints, fold axis and shear zone were collected. Trend and other structural data related of planar and linear features have been measured in different rock units of the study area. The study area is characterized by the presence of asymmetrical to symmetrical and isoclinal open folds. However based on the position of the axial plane a number of symmetrical folds have been identified for quantitative analysis of hinge thickness.

2. GEOLOGY AND STRUCTURE OF THE AREA: The study area lies in the eastern and southern part of the Mahoba district where geological mapping was carried out. The area is famous for the well known NW-SE trending dolerite dykes. Lithologically this region is mainly characterized by different types of granite forming Bundelkhand granite, gneisses, mafic dykes, mafic enclave and metamorphites. The rock type of area can be classified as igneous rocks and metamorphites. Igneous rocks of the area have been classified as acidic and basic varieties where granites are the acidic rocks while dolerite dykes are the basic one. The metamorphites of the area is represented by amphibolites and gneisses (Figure I). The rocks of the area have suffered folding, faulting and shearing.

In Bijanagar Sagar dam site, NE-SW trending fractures have displaced quartz and epidote veins from 0.5cm to 1.5cms. Grey granite is marked by horst and graben structure developed by displacement of eastern and western limb of quartz vein by $N80^{\circ}E-S80^{\circ}W$ and $N50^{\circ}E-S50^{\circ}W$ orientation of mesoscopic faults respectively. Another N-S oriented fracture in western limb is filled by quartz. The extent of displacement by both side shear fractures is towards north resulting in development of graben structure. In Bijanagar (Panchi Vihar) area mylonite is traversed by $N55^{\circ}E-S55^{\circ}W$ oriented epidote veins which are displaced 6cm by $N40^{\circ}E-S40^{\circ}W$ oriented faults. $N60^{\circ}E-S60^{\circ}W$ trending mylonite zone is displaced towards SE in enechelon fashion by $N35^{\circ}W-S35^{\circ}E$ oriented fractures. Fractures parallel to mylonite zone have further displaced veins by 5cm towards north in porphyritic granite. The orientation of youngest epidote vein is $N20^{\circ}W$. A pipe like quartz vein is found to be oriented in $N40^{\circ}E-S40^{\circ}W$.

In Paswara area S fabric in mylonites strike in $N70^{\circ}W-S70^{\circ}E$ while C fabrics are aligned in $N25^{\circ}W-S25^{\circ}E$. The rocks are marked by isoclinally folded quartz veins which are common. The other older and younger veins are oriented in $N80^{\circ}W-S80^{\circ}E$ and $N20^{\circ}E-S20^{\circ}W$ respectively. The vein is marked by N-S and E-W oriented fractures. Second generation of quartz vein oriented in ENE-WSW has displaced the earlier one by 2 feet towards south.

Granite in the Churbara area is marked by 2cm to 5cm NW-SE area trending in $N15^{\circ}W-S15^{\circ}E$ and is dissected by $N75^{\circ}W-S75^{\circ}E$ trending another veins. Fractures are oriented in $N40^{\circ}W-S40^{\circ}E$. Three sets of joints are noticed. Trends of these joints are in NNW-SSE, WNW-ESE and ENE-WSW.

Figure I: Geological map of the study area

3. FOLD ANALYSIS: The study area is characterized by asymmetrical to symmetrical and isoclinal and open folds. Quantitative analysis of hinge and limb variation, limb thickness and limb axial angle of naturally folded strata has been carried out on the basis of measures obtained for geometrical aspect of hinge thickness and its implications for

symmetrical fold genesis in elucidating the stage of folds. For such study 11 symmetrical folds were traced from various outcrops of Mahoba district.

4. METHODOLOGY: For the quantitative analysis of hinge thickness the following method was adopted. First of all to obtain the profile of T-folds symmetrical folds traced from the various outcrop of studied area in Mahoba district. The traced folds were transferred on to a graph such that the axial surface was considered on Y axis. A base line was drawn perpendicular to this datum line where the limb end was obtained (figure II). The folds seen in the field were traced and their symmetrical developments have been discussed.

The hinge thickness (Th) is the thickness of the fold along the hinge i.e. along the axial line. The limb thickness (T_l) is orthogonal thickness of the limb at their lowest points i.e. along the base line usually; this thickness is found equal for both limbs. This study T_l has been taken as mean thickness of both limbs.

The thickness ration (T) have been determined by dividing hinge thickness by limb thickness i.e. $T = Th/T_l$.

The axial angle (α) has been measured from a given traced for arc (inner or outer) of a folds as subtended at the apex (hinge). In the present work mean α has been taken to represent the axial angle of particular (T) fold and is given by

$$\alpha = \alpha_i + \alpha_o/2$$

The orthogonal thickness (T_l) of the limb of the fold along the base line and the thickness (Th) along the hinge have been measured and thickness ratio Th/T_l obtained. The axial angle of the inner α_i and that of the outer α_o curves and their mean $\alpha = \alpha_i + \alpha_o/2$ have been measured.

To obtained value of wavelength and aptitude the length of the wave measured from one and the centre of datum line. Up to the hinge of the fold and the ration from determined by dividing. The values of wavelength by amplitude which have been given in table I.

Figure II: Tracing from the some selected natural folds as studies in the area Bijanagar Sagar, Paswara and Churbara of Mahoba district.

S.N.	Th(cm)	T ₁ (cm)			T=Th/T ₁	α ₁ (degree)	α ₀ (degree)	α=α ₁ +α ₀ /2	Wave length/Amplitude (W/A)
		Left	Right	Mean					
1	0.7	0.5	0.4	0.45	1.55	48°	54°	51	0.097
2	0.6	0.9	0.7	0.8	0.75	100°	105°	102.5	2.3
3	1.4	1	0.9	0.95	1.47	128°	116°	122	4.3
4	2	1.3	1.2	1.25	1.6	75°	74°	74.5	0.2
5	0.9	0.9	1.7	1.3	0.69	102°	104°	103	2.6
6	0.7	0.6	0.3	0.45	1.55	52°	54°	53	1.05
7	0.9	0.5	0.3	0.4	2.25	78°	65°	71.5	2.1
8	1.8	1.4	0.6	1	1.8	80°	86°	83	1.4
9	1.6	0.9	0.8	0.85	1.88	106°	95°	100.5	2.6
10	0.4	0.6	0.4	0.5	0.8	110°	106°	108	2.6
11	1.5	1.8	1.9	1.85	0.81	135°	126°	130.5	4.3

Table I: Values of wavelength/amplitude ration were also obtained shown in table.

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION: Field of parallel folds in which both the thickness Th, T₁ and T_α plot in the graph show maximum 130.5° value of α. As the values of α is reduced the hinge zone of fold keep on developing thickness due to intensity of deformation. Fold no. 3 shows increase of T with decrease of α at the second last maximum α value but value of α is in between 102.5° to 108° the T is reduced in the fold no. 10, 5 and 2 suddenly below one and for majority of these folds maintains same trends i.e. at this α° T remains constant. Further as the values of α decrease, the values of T increases rapidly and show inverse relationship except in fold no. 1 and 6 where below 54° the T value remains constant. Bhattacharya (10) also observed that for α more than 130° does not show any variation and maintain a value of unity i.e. it shows the field of parallel folds in which both T and α plot in the graph show same values. From these data it may be said that symmetrical folds have inversely proportional relationship between T and α in the range of T from 1.6 to 2.25 and α from 55° to 100.5°.

Figure: III Plots of the thickness ratio (T) against the axial angle (α°) for the fold observed in the study area. Each point represents the estimate value for the traced folds.

With regard to wavelength/amplitude ratio it has been found that folds having less axial angle are characterized by low value of wavelength/amplitude i.e. 0.097 for fold no. 1 as shown in figure III. Whereas an increase in α value shows respective increase in the value of wavelength/amplitude of the folds reaching 4.3 for fold no. 11 in the study area. Thus it may be said that early formed folds are characterized by relatively lower values of the wavelength/amplitude ratio which generally increase for the folds of later generation, thus the earlier folds appear to have relatively lower values of wavelength/amplitude than the later folds due to sequential effect of influence of the later phases of deformation.

6. CONCLUSION: Lithologically the study area is mainly characterized by different types of granite, gneisses, mafic dykes and metamorphites. The rock of the area has suffered folding, faulting and shearing. Wavelength/ amplitude ratio suggests that the folds having less axial angle are characterized by low value of wavelength/ amplitude i.e. 0.097. Increase in α values show respective increase in the value of wavelength/ amplitude of the fold reaching upto 4.3. Earlier formed folds are characterized by relatively lower values of the wavelength/amplitude ratio which generally increases for the folds of later generation. Hence the earlier folds appear to have relatively lower values than the later folds due to sequential effect of influence of the later phases of deformation.

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